

ISOLATION OF MICROORGANISMS INVOLVED IN CELLULASE BIOSYNTHESIS AND THEIR BIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS

A. Yasenjiang¹, Z. Karimova², E. Xaitboyeva³, J. Boyxonov⁴,
N.N. Sultanov⁵, S.A. Abdusamatov⁶

National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20047228>

Abstract. *This article analyzes microorganisms involved in the biosynthesis of cellulase enzymes, as well as their biological and enzymatic characteristics. The study evaluates the significance of highly active micromycetes in the bioconversion of lignocellulosic plant residues, particularly *Trichoderma asperellum* and *Chaetomium globosum* strains. The results demonstrate that these fungi actively synthesize a complex of cellulolytic enzymes and are capable of efficiently degrading a variety of substrates.*

During the study, solid-state fermentation conditions were employed using wheat straw, corn stalk, and other lignocellulosic substrates, and an increase in reducing sugars as well as total protein content was recorded. Furthermore, the morphological and cultural characteristics, growth conditions, and enzymatic activity of the microorganisms were determined, and their potential application in biotechnological processes was substantiated.

The results indicate that cellulase-producing microorganisms represent promising biological agents for the processing of plant residues, as well as for the production of biofeed and enzyme preparations.

Keywords: *cellulase, lignocellulose, bioconversion, micromycetes, *Trichoderma asperellum*, *Chaetomium globosum*, enzymatic activity, solid-state fermentation, reducing sugars, biotechnology, plant residues.*

Introduction

Cellulose is one of the most abundant organic polymers in nature and constitutes the principal structural component of plant cell walls. Despite the annual generation of vast amounts of lignocellulosic biomass on Earth, a significant portion remains inefficiently utilized. For this reason, enzymes capable of biologically degrading cellulose—namely cellulases—are gaining increasing importance.

Cellulase enzymes are primarily synthesized by various microorganisms, particularly fungi and bacteria. They hydrolyze cellulose molecules into simple sugars, a process that plays a crucial role in the production of biofuels, feed additives, and other biotechnological products. In particular, micromycetes such as *Trichoderma asperellum* and *Chaetomium globosum* are distinguished by their high cellulolytic activity and are widely applied at the industrial scale.

In recent years, there has been a growing demand for environmentally friendly methods for the processing of lignocellulosic raw materials. Compared to chemical approaches, microbiological bioconversion methods are considered more economically and ecologically efficient. Therefore, the identification of microorganisms capable of active cellulase production, the study of their properties, and their application under optimal conditions constitute an important scientific objective.

From this perspective, investigating microorganisms involved in cellulase biosynthesis and their characteristics is of both scientific and practical relevance, and the present article is devoted to this issue.

Literature Review. If not properly managed in a timely manner, secondary plant products (i.e., residues) can cause environmental harm, contributing to greenhouse gas emissions or leading to soil and water contamination during decomposition. Numerous studies have demonstrated that biotechnological approaches can serve as effective solutions for utilizing such materials without causing environmental damage [1].

Microbial strains, particularly fungal strains, possess the ability to utilize cellulose as a source of carbon and energy. Fungi and bacteria with this capability must be able to synthesize enzymes that degrade these complex polymers. Cellulases are widely applied in various industries, including food and animal feed production, textiles, paper manufacturing, and wastewater treatment [2].

The use of plant residues as a carbon source in the composition of the culture medium has been shown in numerous studies to significantly enhance the cellulolytic activity of fungi belonging to the *Trichoderma* genus. For example, rice straw has been demonstrated to be a more effective carbon source than carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) for cellulase enzyme production by the *T. harzianum* MTSS8230 strain [3].

Enzymes that degrade cellulose represent key tools for achieving the efficient reutilization of biomass. The fungus *T. harzianum* is capable of synthesizing cellulolytic enzymes responsible for cellulose degradation. However, one of the major components of the natural biocomplex—lignin—confers structural resistance to cellulose, rendering the complex resistant to hydrolysis. On average, plant biomass consists of approximately 23% lignin, 40% cellulose, and 33% hemicellulose by weight [4].

Plant cell walls constitute the most abundant renewable source of fermentable sugars on Earth, with plants producing more than 50×10^9 tons of cellulose annually. The total global reserves of cellulose exceed 10^{12} tons. The majority of cellulose is synthesized in plants as a result of photosynthesis [5].

Understanding the relationships between the genes responsible for enzymatic cellulose hydrolysis and the synergistic reactions involved is of critical importance for improving biomass biodegradation technologies. The synergistic interactions, transcriptomes, exoproteomes, and enzymatic activities of *T. harzianum*, *T. reesei*, and *T. atroviride* extracts have been characterized [6].

In order to better understand and reproduce the efficiency of these reactions, the scientific community has conducted numerous studies aimed at identifying and characterizing the enzymes required for the degradation of various components of lignocellulose, as well as determining the interactions between lignocellulosic components and the enzymes involved in their degradation [8].

Furthermore, the cultivation of producers on solid media is considered important for obtaining high yields of cellulase enzymes. However, the use of solid substrates also has certain limitations: the growth of producers under such conditions is more difficult to control. In addition, a portion of the enzymes synthesized by the producers may remain bound to residual solid substrates [9].

It has been established that the enzymatic system responsible for the conversion of cellulose into glucose includes at least three types of cellulases: endoglucanase (endo-1,4- β -D-glucanase,

EG, EC 3.2.1.4), cellobiohydrolase or exoglucanase (exo-1,4- β -D-glucanase, CBH, EC 3.2.1.91), and β -glucosidase (1,4- β -D-glucanase, BG, EC 3.2.1.21). Endoglucanase acts randomly along the cellulose chain to generate shorter cellulose fragments. Cellobiohydrolase functions as an exoglucanase, releasing the disaccharide cellobiose. Subsequently, β -glucosidase hydrolyzes cellobiose to produce glucose [5].

Numerous scientific studies have been conducted by various researchers on protein synthesis in *Trichoderma* fungi. In this review, we summarize findings since 2014 regarding proteins produced by *Trichoderma*, their origins, terminators, signal proteins, yields, and commonly applied fields, and provide an overview of the strategies used to advance this line of research [7].

Materials and Methods

Isolation and Screening of Cellulolytic Micromycetes from Natural Sources. To isolate cellulose-degrading micromycetes, samples were collected from various ecological sources. In particular, soil, plant residues (wheat straw and corn stalks), wood debris, and rhizosphere samples were obtained from different locations in Tashkent city as well as the Kashkadarya and Bukhara regions, and were stored at 4°C until transported to the laboratory.

Micromycetes were isolated using serial dilution and direct plating methods of soil samples. For cultivation, Czapek–Dox medium (g/L: sucrose – 30.0 or glucose – 20.0; NaNO₃ – 3.0; K₂HPO₄ – 1.0; MgSO₄·7H₂O – 0.5; KCl – 0.5; FeSO₄·7H₂O – 0.01) and Mandels mineral medium (g/L: KH₂PO₄ – 2.0; (NH₄)₂HPO₄ – 1.4; MgSO₄ – 0.5; CaCl₂ – 0.3; urea – 0.3; peptone – 1.0; sucrose – 2.0) were used. After sterilization, tetracycline was added to the media at a concentration of 300 μ g/mL to prevent bacterial contamination. Incubation was carried out at 28–30°C for 3–6 days.

The resulting colonies were transferred to subculture, and purification was performed through repeated inoculation of spores or mycelial fragments. When necessary, Triton X-100 was added to the medium to facilitate the isolation of pure cultures. As a result, several micromycete isolates were obtained, from which strains exhibiting cellulolytic activity were selected.

The isolated micromycetes were characterized based on macromorphological features (colony color, structure, and growth rate) and micromorphological traits (structure of mycelium, conidiophores, and conidia). Microscopic observations were carried out using a light microscope with 400 \times magnification. The systematic position of the fungi was determined according to modern mycological identification keys and relevant literature.

Screening for cellulolytic activity was conducted in two stages. In the first stage, isolates were cultivated on filter paper moistened with Mandels medium and evaluated for their ability to degrade cellulose. The most active strains were then subjected to a second stage, where they were grown in a modified liquid Mandels medium (pH 5.5–5.8) supplemented with 2% wheat bran, corn stalk, and other cellulosic substrates, at 28–30°C on a rotary shaker at 200–220 rpm for 4 days.

During the study, the cellulase and xylanase activities of the strains, their protein synthesis capacity, and their ability to enrich cellulosic substrates with reducing sugars were determined, and the most active micromycete strains were selected. These strains were subsequently used as the primary objects for further investigations [10].

Genomic DNA Extraction Method. Genomic DNA from the selected cellulolytic micromycete strains was isolated using the classical phenol–chloroform extraction method. This approach enables the recovery of high-quality and purified DNA from fungal cells.

Fungal biomass grown in liquid culture medium was centrifuged at $2500 \times g$ for 15 minutes, and the resulting cell pellet was collected. A 2 g sample of frozen mycelium was then ground in a mortar using liquid nitrogen to mechanically disrupt the cell wall.

For cell lysis, a specialized extraction solution preheated to 55°C was used. This solution contained triisopropylphenyl sulfonic acid (TNS), p-aminosalicylic acid (PAS), deionized water, Tris-HCl, NaCl, EDTA buffer, and phenol. These components function to disrupt the cell membrane and proteins, thereby facilitating the release of DNA into the solution.

The mixture was incubated at 55°C under continuous agitation, after which 5 mL of chloroform was added and incubation was continued. Subsequently, the mixture was centrifuged at $2500 \times g$ for 15 minutes to achieve phase separation. The upper (aqueous) phase was carefully collected and transferred to a new tube.

For DNA purification, an equal volume of phenol–chloroform (1:1) was added to the aqueous phase, mixed using a vortex, and centrifuged again. This step ensured the removal of proteins and other impurities. In the subsequent step, chloroform alone was added, followed by centrifugation, and the resulting supernatant was transferred to a new tube.

To precipitate genomic DNA, 30 μL of 3.0 M sodium acetate (pH 5.2) and 25 μL of 96% ethanol were added, and the samples were incubated for approximately 18 hours. Thereafter, the samples were centrifuged at $14,000 \times g$ for 30 minutes at 4°C , and the DNA pellet was collected.

The DNA pellet was washed with 70% ethanol and centrifuged again at $14,000 \times g$ for 10 minutes at 4°C . Subsequently, the DNA was air-dried, dissolved in deionized water, and stored at 4°C for further molecular biological analyses [12].

Amplification of rDNA Gene Regions by PCR. For the purpose of molecular identification of micromycete strains, the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region of ribosomal DNA (rDNA) was amplified by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using the isolated genomic DNA as a template. The ITS region is a widely used universal molecular marker for species-level identification of fungi.

For amplification, the primers ITS1 (5'-TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGG-3') and ITS4 (5'-TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC-3') were employed. These primers are complementary to conserved regions of the rDNA gene cluster and enable the amplification of a fragment encompassing the ITS1–5.8S–ITS2 regions.

The PCR reaction was prepared in a total volume of 100 μL , containing 25 ng of genomic DNA, 10 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.3), 50 mM KCl, 1.5 mM MgCl_2 , 0.2 mM each of dNTPs (dATP, dCTP, dGTP, dTTP), 50 ng each of ITS1 and ITS4 primers, and 2.5 units of Taq DNA polymerase.

Amplification was performed in a thermal cycler under the following conditions: initial denaturation at $95\text{--}97^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 minutes, followed by 30 cycles of denaturation (95°C for 30–35 s), annealing ($52\text{--}55^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 45–60 s), and elongation (72°C for 1 minute). A final elongation step was carried out at 72°C for 5–7 minutes.

The PCR products were analyzed by electrophoresis on a 1.4% agarose gel in $1\times\text{TBE}$ (or TAE) buffer. The results were visualized under ultraviolet illumination, and the presence and size of the amplified fragments were evaluated [14].

Determination of the General Characteristics of Selected Micromycete Strains. To determine the morphological and cultural characteristics of selected cellulolytic micromycete strains (*Trichoderma asperellum* and *Chaetomium globosum*), as well as to establish their optimal growth conditions, studies were conducted using various culture media. For this purpose, Mandels,

Czapek, wort agar (diluted to 7° on the saccharometer scale), and potato dextrose agar (PDA) media were prepared.

The prepared media were sterilized at 1.0 atm for 30 minutes and poured into Petri dishes. Subsequently, fungal spores were inoculated and incubated at 29–33°C under thermostat conditions. The macromorphological characteristics of the colonies (color, structure, and growth rate) were observed, while micromorphological features were examined using XSP-136 B and LEICA DM750 light microscopes at 400× magnification.

Mandels medium was evaluated as a favorable substrate for the growth of cellulolytic and enzymatically active micromycetes. Based on this, experiments were conducted to determine the growth dynamics and radial growth rate of the selected strains.

To enhance the economic efficiency of the culture medium and to identify optimal substrates for fungal growth, various cellulose-containing materials were used as carbon sources at a concentration of 2%, including wheat straw, corn stalk, wheat bran, filter paper, and others. Mandels mineral medium was used as the control variant.

To determine the growth rate of fungal colonies, inoculation was performed at the center of Petri dishes, followed by incubation at 29–33°C. The colony radius was measured every 24 hours using a ruler, and average values were calculated.

The radial growth rate was determined using the following formula:

$$Kr = (r - r_0) / (t - t_0)$$

where:

- Kr – radial growth rate (mm/h),
- r_0 – colony radius at the initial time,
- r – colony radius at a given time,
- t_0 and t – time points [10].

In addition, the developmental cycle of the selected micromycete strains was studied in liquid Mandels medium. Observations were carried out using a LEICA DM750 light microscope at 400× magnification. The vegetative and reproductive stages of fungal development were monitored at 30-minute intervals, and the corresponding morphological changes were recorded.

Bioconversion of Plant Residues by Selected Micromycete Strains.

The enzymatic activity of selected micromycete strains (*Trichoderma asperellum* and *Chaetomium globosum*) was utilized to study the bioconversion processes of cellulose-containing plant raw materials. During the experiments, enzyme complexes isolated from the fungal culture liquid were applied to the degradation of cellulosic substrates.

Fungal cultures grown in liquid medium were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes, and the mycelium was separated from the culture liquid. Under solid-state fermentation conditions, following the completion of fermentation, either the entire mass of the culture medium mixture or an aqueous extract (filtrate) obtained by pressing was used. In this process, the following ratio was applied: 10 units of cellulolytic activity per 1 g of treated substrate.

For the development of the solid-state fermentation regime, pretreated aboveground biomass of corn stalk and winter wheat straw were used as raw materials. These substrates were dried to a moisture content of 6–7% and ground to a particle size of 1.5–2.0 mm.

Under laboratory conditions, the fermentation process was carried out in 1 L Erlenmeyer flasks. In semi-industrial conditions, cultivation was performed in specialized trays (30 × 40 cm) with a substrate layer not exceeding 50–55 mm in height. The culture medium was prepared based

on the Mandels formulation and supplemented with ground wheat (50%) and corn stalk (50%), or straw moistened with mineral medium. The initial pH was maintained within the range of 4.7–4.9.

As inoculum material, 5-day-old fungal cultures grown on Czapek–Dox agar and Mandels mineral medium were used. The inoculum itself consisted of a suspension of culture liquid obtained from growth on corn stalk and wheat-based substrates.

Under solid-state fermentation conditions, the degree of hydrolysis of wheat bran, corn stalk, and wheat straw using selected micromycete strains was investigated. As a result, the formation of reducing sugars and an increase in total protein content were observed, allowing the efficiency of the bioconversion process to be evaluated.

Determination of Reducing Sugars in the Enzyme Preparation. The content of reducing sugars was determined using the Somogyi–Nelson method. This method is based on the quantitative determination of reducing sugars formed as a result of cellulose hydrolysis under the action of cellulolytic enzymes.

Determination of Cellulolytic Enzyme Activity. The activity of cellulolytic enzymes was determined using a slightly modified Mandels & Weber method, based on measuring the amount of reducing products formed as a result of enzyme action on specific substrates (Na-CMC and filter paper).

Procedure. A mixture of substrate and enzyme (culture liquid) was incubated in 15–20 mL test tubes at 50°C in a water bath. After incubation, 1.0 mL of Somogyi reagent was added. The reaction mixture was then heated in a boiling water bath for 20 minutes, followed by cooling with cold water. Subsequently, 1.0 mL of Nelson reagent was added and mixed thoroughly. Each sample was transferred into a 25 mL volumetric flask and diluted to volume with distilled water. For the control, 1.0 mL of sodium acetate buffer (0.1 M, pH 5.5) was used.

The optical density of the reducing substances was measured at a wavelength of 610 nm using a Shimadzu UV-1800 spectrophotometer. The concentration of reducing sugars was determined based on a calibration curve constructed using glucose as a standard. One unit of cellulase activity was defined as the amount of enzyme required to produce 1 mg of reducing substances (expressed as glucose equivalents) under the experimental conditions.

The activity of exo-1,4- β -glucanase was determined using filter paper as a substrate. The filter paper was cut into 2–3 mm fragments, and 50 mg was accurately weighed and incubated with the enzyme at 50°C and pH 5.5 for 1 hour. Enzyme activity was then calculated based on the amount of glucose released.

The activity of endo-1,4- β -glucanase was determined by measuring the amount of reducing sugars formed in a reaction mixture containing 0.5 mL of 1.0% Na-CMC (degree of substitution – 0.86, degree of polymerization – 800) prepared in 0.1 M sodium acetate buffer (pH 5.5) and 0.5 mL of culture liquid. The mixture was incubated at 50°C, and the released reducing sugars were quantified. One unit of endo-1,4- β -glucanase activity was defined as the amount of enzyme that produces 1.0 mg of glucose under the conditions of 50°C and pH 5.5 within 30 minutes [12].

Determination of Xylanase Activity. Xylan obtained from the core of corn cobs was used as a substrate. Xylanase activity was determined based on the enzyme's action on a 1% xylan solution. The amount of reducing substances formed was measured using the Somogyi–Nelson method. A calibration curve was constructed using xylose as a standard. One unit of xylanase activity was defined as the amount of enzyme required to produce 1 mg of xylose under the experimental conditions [11].

Results and Discussion

Analysis of Morphological and Cultural Characteristics of Isolated Fungi. At present, micromycetes belonging to various taxonomic groups of fungi, particularly the genera *Trichoderma*, *Penicillium*, and *Chaetomium*, are widely distributed in nature and are distinguished by their high enzymatic activity. As with all microorganisms, the proper progression of physiological and biochemical processes in these fungi depends on the selection of optimal environmental conditions. Therefore, in the course of this study, optimal growth conditions were established for the isolated strains, and their morphological as well as biological characteristics were investigated.

To determine the structural and biological characteristics of the studied strains, they were analyzed using light microscopy. According to the results, colonies of the *Trichoderma asperellum* strain were initially white, gradually turning light green and subsequently dark green during incubation. The mycelium was hyaline, with a cotton-like or spider web-like appearance, and was characterized by rapid growth.

The conidiophores were tree-like and regularly branched, bearing flask-shaped phialides (2–3 µm in width and 5–7 µm in length), typically arranged in groups of 2–5 on the branches. The conidia were green, aggregated in mucilaginous heads, and exhibited a spherical to slightly ellipsoidal shape (2.5–3.2 × 2.7–3.0 µm). They contributed to the formation of a dark green coloration and, as a result of active sporulation, promoted the development of aerial hyphae.

Colonies of the *Penicillium canescens* strain were found to be typically light green to grayish-green in color, with a velvety or powdery surface appearance. The mycelium was hyaline, well developed, and densely spread over the substrate surface.

The conidiophores were branched and exhibited a characteristic three-part (penicillus-type) structure, consisting of sequentially arranged metulae and phialides. The phialides were cylindrical or slightly flask-shaped (2–3 µm in width and 6–9 µm in length), typically arranged in groups of 3–6 on the metulae. The conidia formed through these structures were arranged in chains, with a spherical to ellipsoidal shape (2.0–3.0 µm), imparting a powdery appearance to the colony.

Colonies of the *Chaetomium globosum* strain were initially white, gradually turning yellowish or grayish during incubation. The mycelium was dense and cottony in structure.

In this fungus, classical conidiophores were poorly developed, and reproduction predominantly occurred through the formation of perithecial-type fruiting bodies. The perithecia were spherical to oval in shape, with surfaces covered by hair-like structures (setae). Within these structures, asci were formed, in which ascospores developed. The ascospores were lemon-shaped or ellipsoidal, dark in color, and were released into the environment upon maturation.

Based on morphological and microscopic characteristics, the studied strains were clearly distinguished from one another. *Trichoderma asperellum* was characterized by its rapid growth and green-spored structure; *Penicillium canescens* by its brush-like conidiophores and chain-forming conidia; and *Chaetomium globosum* by its ability to form perithecia. These features not only confirm their taxonomic identity but also substantiate their potential applications in biotechnological processes (Figure 1).

As a result of studying the morphological and cultural characteristics, fungi belonging to the genera *Trichoderma* and *Chaetomium globosum* were identified among the isolates obtained during the study. These findings were confirmed based on their colonial, microscopic, and sporulation features.

According to modern classification, fungi of the genus *Trichoderma* belong to the phylum *Ascomycota*, class *Sordariomycetes*, order *Hypocreales*, and family *Hypocreaceae*.

Representatives of this genus are characterized by rapid growth, the formation of green-colored spores, and high enzymatic activity.

Figure 1. Light microscopic view of *Trichoderma* sp. S3 and *Chaetomium* sp. S18: 1 – conidia, 2 – phialide, 3 – conidiophore (Microscope: Leica DM 750; magnification 400×).

Chaetomium globosum belongs to the phylum *Ascomycota*, class *Sordariomycetes*, order *Sordariales*, and family *Chaetomiaceae*, and is distinguished by the formation of perithecial-type fruiting bodies. These fungi are notable for their ability to degrade lignocellulosic substrates and for their high biomass production capacity.

The morphological and cultural characteristics of the isolated strains—including growth rate, colony color and appearance, optimal temperature and pH values, as well as growth behavior on various solid agar media (Czapek, Mandels, potato dextrose agar, Sabouraud, and wort agar)—were investigated. Based on the experimental results, the optimal growth conditions were determined to be within the temperature range of 29–33°C and a pH range of 5–6.

During the study, different plant residues (wheat straw, wheat bran, other lignocellulosic substrates, and filter paper) were added to Mandels medium at a concentration of 2% as carbon sources. The rate of colony formation and the degree of substrate utilization by the fungal strains were subsequently evaluated.

According to the results, *Trichoderma* strains were distinguished by rapid and intensive growth on almost all culture media tested. The colonies typically developed from light green to dark green in color, exhibiting a granular and highly sporulating structure. In the central part of the colony, the mycelium was dense, cottony, and spider web-like in appearance, while increased sporulation over time resulted in a darker coloration.

In contrast, *Chaetomium* sp. strains formed relatively dense colonies with yellowish-brown to olive coloration. Although the mycelium was well developed, sporulation was comparatively less pronounced. These fungi were characterized by their ability to uniformly cover the substrate surface and their tendency toward substantial biomass production.

The results of the study demonstrated that the isolated fungi possess the ability to modify the structure of substrates prepared from various plant residues and effectively utilize them, actively participating in the hydrolysis of lignocellulosic compounds. In particular, *Trichoderma* strains were found to intensively synthesize cellulase enzyme complexes and rapidly degrade substrates, indicating their high efficiency in bioconversion processes.

It was also observed that, under identical temperature conditions, the growth rate of the fungi varied across different culture media. This variation is primarily associated with differences in the chemical composition of the substrates and the availability of carbon sources (Figure 2).

During the study, the macromorphological and cultural characteristics of the isolated micromycete strains were examined by cultivation in Petri dishes. The results showed that the isolates differed significantly in terms of colony color, shape, structure, degree of sporulation, and

radial growth rate. This diversity indicates that the isolated microorganisms belong to different taxonomic groups and exhibit distinct physiological characteristics.

Figure 2. Colonies of the isolated micromycete isolates on Mandels medium (n = 5).

The green to dark green, powdery-textured, and rapidly growing colonies observed in the figure are characteristic of fungi belonging to the genus *Trichoderma*. Such colonies are distinguished by a high level of sporulation, rapid radial expansion from the center toward the periphery, and a granular surface structure. These features indicate their high cellulolytic activity and their ability to efficiently degrade lignocellulosic substrates.

In some colonies, yellowish or golden pigmentation, as well as concentric ring-like growth radiating from the center, was observed. These features may be characteristic of fungi belonging to the genera *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium*. These fungi are also capable of synthesizing cellulolytic enzymes and play an important role in biotechnological processes.

In addition, white, cottony or fluffy colonies exhibiting rapid growth but relatively low sporulation were also observed. Such characteristics may be typical of fungi belonging to the genera *Mucor* or *Rhizopus*, or may correspond to young colonies that have not yet reached the sporulation stage.

Overall, among the isolated micromycetes, fungi belonging to the genus *Trichoderma* were distinguished by their rapid growth and intensive sporulation, demonstrating their potential as promising producers for the bioconversion of cellulosic substrates. At the same time, fungi such

as *Chaetomium globosum* are of particular importance due to their capacity for substantial biomass production. It should be noted that these identifications were primarily based on macromorphological characteristics.

Potato dextrose agar (PDA), Czapek, and wort agar media were found to be favorable for the growth of *Trichoderma* sp. and *Chaetomium globosum* strains isolated in this study. On these media, the fungi exhibited rapid growth and formed circular colonies within a short period. In *Trichoderma* strains, colonies were predominantly light green, with a gradual transition to darker green shades during sporulation. On potato dextrose agar, initially white mycelia were formed, which later developed a green coloration.

On Mandels medium, *Trichoderma* strains formed uniformly growing, cottony colonies, and by 72 hours of incubation, granular mycelial structures appeared in the central region. The colony density on this medium was high, and overall development was more pronounced compared to other media. The colonies were initially whitish, gradually changing to light green and then dark green over time.

On Czapek medium, the growth of *Trichoderma* strains was relatively slower; colonies were initially white and later turned light green, with the mycelium forming ring-like structures.

In contrast, *Chaetomium globosum* strains produced relatively dense colonies with yellowish-brown to olive coloration. These fungi were characterized by well-developed mycelia that uniformly covered the substrate surface. Although sporulation was less pronounced compared to *Trichoderma*, a higher capacity for biomass production was observed.

In experiments conducted on Mandels medium supplemented with 2% plant residues (wheat straw, wheat bran, and filter paper), *Trichoderma* strains exhibited very rapid growth, covering the entire surface of the Petri dish within 72 hours of incubation. The colonies were circular, with a uniform granular and segmented structure, and a dense accumulation of mycelium was observed in the central region. By 96 hours, the colonies had developed a completely dark green coloration.

On the medium supplemented with wheat bran, the formation of light yellow mycelium in the central part of the colony was observed, indicating the influence of substrate composition on fungal metabolism.

It was also determined that the growth rate of fungal colonies varied depending on the type of culture medium, with significantly accelerated radial growth observed in variants where additional carbon sources were incorporated into Mandels medium. During the experiments, the strains were cultivated at 29–32°C, and the colony radius was measured every 24 hours.

The results demonstrated that *Trichoderma* strains exhibited a high growth rate, covering the entire surface of the Petri dish within 72 hours. In media supplemented with plant residues, the colony diameter reached up to 90 mm, whereas in the control variant it was 79 mm. This confirms that lignocellulosic substrates serve as important stimulatory factors for fungal growth. At the same time, although *Chaetomium globosum* strains showed relatively slower growth, they were distinguished by their high biomass production capacity.

In media supplemented with corn stalks and wheat bran, it was observed as early as the second day of incubation that the radial growth rate of colonies was higher compared to other variants. In *Trichoderma* strains, the growth rate reached 0.82 mm/h in corn stalk-based medium and 0.87 mm/h in wheat bran-supplemented medium. In contrast, the *Chaetomium globosum* strain exhibited growth rates of 0.87 mm/h in corn stalk-based medium and 0.92 mm/h in wheat bran-supplemented medium.

At the same time, *Chaetomium globosum* strains exhibited more intensive growth, with radial growth rates higher than those of *Trichoderma*. This indicates a strong capacity of this fungus for the effective utilization of lignocellulosic substrates and for substantial biomass production.

In addition, relatively high growth rates were also recorded for both fungal strains on media supplemented with wheat straw; however, these values were slightly lower compared to those observed in media based on corn stalks and wheat bran.

The obtained results confirm that the chemical composition of lignocellulosic substrates directly influences the growth rate of fungi. In particular, the faster growth and higher biomass production of *Chaetomium globosum* highlight its importance as a key organism in substrate bioconversion processes, while *Trichoderma* strains are distinguished by their high enzymatic activity.

Molecular Identification of the Selected Active Strains. Many taxa of micromycetes have traditionally been identified based on morphological criteria. To confirm or refute these identifications, nucleotide sequencing of specific genes has been employed. Therefore, genetic analysis is used as a complementary approach to morphological diagnostics of species.

As indicated in the literature review, it is often difficult to distinguish certain fungal species based solely on biological characteristics. For this reason, the genetic concept of phylogenetic species recognition (GCPSR), based on DNA sequence data, has been widely accepted as an effective method to complement or verify the results obtained through morphological approaches in species identification.

In our study, sequencing of the ITS1–ITS4 rRNA region of the active strain revealed the following nucleotide sequence.

Figure 3. Phylogenetic tree constructed for the active strains.

Constructing a phylogenetic tree based on the analysis of multiple, independent genes is considered the most reliable approach for accurately determining the phylogenetic position of organisms. Based on the obtained nucleotide sequences, a phylogenetic tree of the studied strain was constructed (Figure 3).

Heterokaryosis plays a significant role in the life cycle of fungi. Many species possess haploid nuclei, allowing both dominant and recessive genes to be subject to selection, as recessive genes are not masked by dominant alleles. However, in heterokaryotic cells containing both dominant and recessive alleles of a gene, only the dominant phenotype is expressed, while the recessive allele remains unexpressed. Thus, heterokaryosis resembles a diploid condition in maintaining hidden genetic variability.

For all living organisms in nature, including micromycetes, the proper progression of biochemical and physiological processes requires the selection of an optimal nutrient medium and suitable growth conditions.

In order to determine optimal culture conditions and to reduce the economic cost of the medium, a series of experiments was conducted. The strains were cultivated on several types of media, and it was established that Mandels medium supported the most rapid growth. To make the medium more cost-effective, a modified formulation was prepared by omitting peptone, urea, and sucrose, and instead incorporating 2% cellulosic substrates as the primary carbon source (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Enzymatic activity of *Trichoderma sp. S1* and *Chaetomium globosum (S18)*.

The results of the study revealed dynamic changes in the activity of cellulolytic enzymes—endo-1,4-β-glucanase, exo-1,4-β-glucanase, and xylanase—in *Trichoderma sp. S1* and *Chaetomium globosum (S18)* strains during incubation. In both strains, enzyme activity increased from the initial days, reached a maximum on the 4th day, and then gradually declined on days 5–6.

In *Trichoderma sp. S1*, endo-1,4-β-glucanase activity increased from 2.71 U/mL on day 1 to 6.12 U/mL on day 4, followed by a decrease to 5.97 U/mL on day 5 and 4.57 U/mL on day 6. Exo-1,4-β-glucanase exhibited a similar pattern, rising from 1.1 U/mL to 4.3 U/mL and then declining to 3.82 and 2.94 U/mL in subsequent days. Xylanase activity showed the highest increase, rising from 3.89 U/mL to 8.87 U/mL on day 4, and then decreasing to 7.76 and 5.75 U/mL. In the control variant, enzyme activities remained comparatively low (2.89, 1.5, and 4.17 U/mL, respectively), indicating that the addition of substrates stimulates enzyme synthesis.

In the *Chaetomium globosum (S18)* strain, enzyme activity also exhibited an increasing trend, with maximum values recorded on day 4. Endo-1,4-β-glucanase activity increased from 1.91 U/mL to 5.47 U/mL, exo-1,4-β-glucanase from 0.7 U/mL to 3.53 U/mL, and xylanase from 3.22

U/mL to 8.06 U/mL. A decline in enzyme activity was observed on days 5–6, which can be attributed to the depletion of readily degradable components in the substrate.

A comparative analysis of the two strains showed that *Trichoderma* sp. S1 exhibited higher activity across all enzymes, with a particularly pronounced advantage in cellulase complex enzymes, including endo- and exo-1,4- β -glucanases. At the same time, *Chaetomium globosum* demonstrated a high level of xylanase production, indicating its ability to degrade the hemicellulose fraction of lignocellulosic substrates. Overall, the optimal incubation period for enzyme synthesis was determined to be 4 days, with *Trichoderma* sp. S1 being more efficient in cellulose degradation, while *Chaetomium globosum* was more effective in the utilization of hemicellulosic components.

To determine the degree of hydrolysis of cellulosic substrates, experiments were conducted under solid-state fermentation conditions. During the fermentation process, *Trichoderma asperellum*, *Chaetomium globosum*, and *Penicillium canescens* strains were used as producers. Spore–mycelial suspensions of these micromycetes were inoculated into the prepared substrates, and the fermentation process was monitored over a period of 15 days.

Filamentous fungi are well adapted to growth in solid-state systems due to their morphological and physiological characteristics. They are distinguished by apical growth, tolerance to low moisture conditions, aerobic metabolism, and the ability to synthesize a rich complex of cellulolytic and hemicellulolytic enzymes. These features enable them to efficiently degrade lignocellulosic substrates.

Table 3. Enzymatic activity of the isolated strain on various cellulosic substrates (n = 6).

№	Exo-1,4- β -glucanase activity (U/mL)			Endo-1,4- β -glucanase activity, U/mL			Xylanase activity, U/mL		
	<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i>	<i>Penicillium canescens</i>	<i>Chaetomium globosum</i>	<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i>	<i>Penicillium canescens</i>	<i>Chaetomium globosum</i>	<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i>	<i>Penicillium canescens</i>	<i>Chaetomium globosum</i>
1	16,82±0,53	23,72±0,94	14,92±0,53	24,42±0,61	32,02±0,90	22,82±0,55	34,02±1,41	47,82±2,15	27,62±1,29
2	25,32±1,05	31,32±0,69	17,82±0,38	40,12±1,80	58,22±2,14	31,12±1,42	49,62±1,88	67,82±2,04	38,62±1,83
3	37,82±1,18	32,32±1,50	26,32±0,86	54,62±1,69	64,12±3,08	37,32±1,44	69,12±1,20	77,02±2,65	51,42±1,65
4	43,82±1,25	49,32±1,85	37,82±0,90	63,52±2,85	69,82±2,54	42,62±1,79	81,42±2,74	85,62±2,29	68,92±2,48
5	49,82±1,99	51,82±1,70	38,52±1,90	67,42±2,60	72,82±3,17	59,32±1,53	77,72±2,40	81,52±3,63	62,52±2,12
6	46,42±1,37	46,32±1,96	35,02±1,41	59,52±2,38	67,42±3,03	56,52±2,23	71,92±3,37	76,32±3,55	59,92±2,40
7	43,42±1,69	41,42±1,85	36,62±1,25	57,82±2,88	63,22±2,23	51,62±0,91	76,52±3,58	75,92±3,26	55,12±1,81
8	39,82±1,83	37,92±1,50	34,92±0,89	61,52±1,69	65,62±1,63	42,42±0,88	79,52±3,13	81,52±2,83	63,52±1,35
9	45,02±1,30	45,02±1,31	34,02±0,99	64,92±1,67	70,52±3,12	51,82±2,32	84,92±2,43	87,62±2,48	72,82±1,55
10	47,82±1,93	53,82±1,70	41,82±1,09	68,72±1,47	79,12±1,53	57,92±2,00	74,62±2,01	78,62±1,86	66,12±2,13
11	41,72±2,03	47,02±2,12	31,62±1,54	52,52±2,57	63,72±3,09	54,22±2,09	62,82±2,81	75,82±2,94	60,22±2,74
12	32,82±0,71	36,52±1,51	21,32±0,76	43,52±2,03	56,52±2,55	44,82±1,83	56,52±2,18	65,92±2,30	53,12±1,82
13	30,32±1,08	24,82±1,13	18,32±0,78	34,82±1,70	47,42±2,27	40,12±1,68	49,02±1,98	59,22±2,71	47,52±0,91
14	25,42±1,00	22,62±0,46	18,82±0,77	28,62±1,19	40,02±1,18	27,92±0,98	45,92±2,08	50,02±2,34	38,72±1,15
15	22,82±0,63	19,82±0,36	16,82±0,81	27,82±1,03	27,22±0,71	24,12±0,70	36,42±1,19	41,62±1,48	24,92±0,67
Control	17,82±0,83	22,32±0,88	16,12±0,64	24,12±0,80	28,52±0,84	18,52±0,89	28,12±1,02	31,52±0,70	23,92±1,05

During solid-state fermentation, key factors influencing fungal growth and enzymatic activity included temperature, medium acidity (pH), and substrate moisture content. These parameters were maintained at optimal levels, and fermentation efficiency was evaluated based on the amount of reducing sugars accumulated in the fermentolysate as well as enzyme activity.

The results demonstrated that all strains were capable of degrading both cellulose and hemicellulose. Enzyme activity increased over time, reaching maximum levels on days 4–5, followed by a subsequent decline. In terms of enzymatic activity, the *Penicillium canescens* strain

exhibited the highest performance, particularly in the synthesis of xylanase and endo-1,4- β -glucanase enzymes.

The *Trichoderma asperellum* strain was distinguished by the stability and complexity of its enzymatic activity, demonstrating the ability to efficiently degrade both cellulose and hemicellulose simultaneously. Although the enzymatic activity of the *Chaetomium globosum* strain was relatively lower, it is notable for its strong capacity to utilize lignocellulosic substrates and its high biomass production. In addition, the studied *Trichoderma hamatum* strain exhibited a moderate level of enzymatic activity and, therefore, was not selected for further investigations.

The table above presents the dynamics of cellulolytic enzyme activities—exo-1,4- β -glucanase, endo-1,4- β -glucanase, and xylanase—in *Trichoderma asperellum*, *Penicillium canescens*, and *Chaetomium globosum* strains over a 15-day period. The obtained results indicate that enzyme synthesis in all three strains follows a time-dependent pattern governed by specific biological regularities.

According to the analysis, enzyme activity in all strains was relatively low during the initial stage of incubation (days 1–3), which can be attributed to the adaptation phase (lag phase) of microorganisms to the substrate. A sharp increase in enzyme activity was observed between days 3 and 5, corresponding to the active growth (log phase). Notably, maximum or near-maximum values for all enzymes were recorded during days 4–5.

In terms of exo-1,4- β -glucanase activity, *Penicillium canescens* demonstrated superior performance. In this strain, enzyme activity increased from 23.72 ± 0.94 U/mL on day 1 to 51.82 ± 1.70 U/mL on day 5, followed by a gradual decline to 19.82 ± 0.36 U/mL by day 15. In *Trichoderma asperellum*, the maximum value reached 49.82 ± 1.99 U/mL on day 5, whereas in *Chaetomium globosum* it was 38.52 ± 1.90 U/mL. These results indicate that *Penicillium canescens* has a higher capacity to degrade the crystalline structure of cellulose.

Similarly, for endo-1,4- β -glucanase activity, the highest values were also recorded in *Penicillium canescens*, reaching 72.82 ± 3.17 U/mL on day 5. In comparison, the maximum activity of this enzyme in *Trichoderma asperellum* was 67.42 ± 2.60 U/mL, while in *Chaetomium globosum* it reached 59.32 ± 1.53 U/mL. This further confirms the high efficiency of *Penicillium canescens* in cleaving internal bonds within the cellulose polymer chain.

Xylanase activity was also observed at high levels in all strains. The highest value was recorded in *Penicillium canescens* on day 9, reaching 87.62 ± 2.48 U/mL. In *Trichoderma asperellum*, the maximum activity was 84.92 ± 2.43 U/mL (day 9), while in *Chaetomium globosum* it reached 72.82 ± 1.55 U/mL. These results indicate that *Penicillium canescens* is also a leading producer of enzymes involved in the degradation of hemicellulose components.

From day 6 onward, a general decline in enzyme activity was observed in all strains, which can be explained by the depletion of easily degradable substrate components, accumulation of metabolic by-products, and the transition to the stationary phase of growth.

In the control variant, the low levels of enzyme activity for all enzymes (exo: 16.12–22.32; endo: 18.52–28.52; xylanase: 23.92–31.52 U/mL) indicate that enzyme synthesis proceeds very weakly in the absence of fungal involvement.

The obtained results demonstrate that *Penicillium canescens* exhibited the highest overall enzymatic activity, while *Trichoderma asperellum* was distinguished by stable and high-level synthesis of a complex of enzymes. Although *Chaetomium globosum* showed relatively lower enzyme activity, it remains significant due to its other biotechnological properties, particularly its high biomass production capacity.

Thus, the combined application of these strains can ensure efficient degradation of lignocellulosic substrates and enhance the overall efficiency of the bioconversion process.

Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrate that cellulase-producing micromycetes isolated from natural sources possess significant potential for the bioconversion of lignocellulosic plant residues. Among the studied strains, *Penicillium canescens* showed the highest overall enzymatic activity, particularly in exo-1,4- β -glucanase, endo-1,4- β -glucanase, and xylanase production. *Trichoderma asperellum* also demonstrated stable and intensive synthesis of cellulolytic enzymes, while *Chaetomium globosum* was distinguished by its effective utilization of substrates and high biomass-forming capacity.

The findings confirm that plant residues such as wheat straw, wheat bran, and corn stalk can serve as effective substrates for fungal growth and enzyme production under solid-state fermentation conditions. Enzyme activity generally increased during the early stages of incubation, reached maximum levels around days 4–5, and then gradually declined. Overall, the selected micromycete strains may be considered promising biological agents for the environmentally friendly processing of agricultural residues, production of enzyme preparations, and development of biofeed technologies.

REFERENCES

1. Bhatia T., Sindhu S. S. Sustainable management of organic agricultural wastes: contributions in nutrients availability, pollution mitigation and crop production //Discover Agriculture. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 130.
2. Liu, X., Quan, J., Li, Y., Wang, X., & Zhao, J. Advancing cellulose degradation through synthetic biology: engineered pathways and microbial systems for sustainable biomass conversion //Journal of Animal Science and Biotechnology. – 2026. – T. 17. – №. 1. – C. 12.
3. Hussain, M. H., Ashraf, K., Abdullah Alqudaimi, R. E., Martuscelli, M., Leu, S. Y., Rehman, S. U., Mohsin, A. From waste to wealth: unlocking the potential of cellulase characteristics for food processing waste management //Foods. – 2025. – T. 14. – №. 21. – C. 3639.
4. Hsin, K. T., Lee, H., Huang, Y. C., Lin, G. J., Lin, P. Y., Lin, Y. C. J., Chen, P. Y. Lignocellulose degradation in bacteria and fungi: cellulosomes and industrial relevance //Frontiers in Microbiology. – 2025. – T. 16. – C. 1583746.
5. Abdusamatov, S., Alimov, J., & Shurigin, V. *Trichoderma harzianum* 857 is an effective destructor of cellulose-containing raw materials //Indian J Environ Sci. – 2020. – T. 16. – №. 3. – C. 113.
6. Druzhinina I. S., Kubicek C. P. Genetic engineering of *Trichoderma reesei* cellulases and their production //Microbial biotechnology. – 2017. – T. 10. – №. 6. – C. 1485-1499.
7. Dutta P., Deb L., Pandey A. K. *Trichoderma*-from lab bench to field application: Looking back over 50 years //Frontiers in Agronomy. – 2022. – T. 4. – C. 932839.
8. Chen, M., Li, Q., Liu, C., Meng, E., & Zhang, B. Microbial degradation of lignocellulose for sustainable biomass utilization and future research perspectives //Sustainability. – 2025. – T. 17. – №. 9. – C. 4223.
9. Sahu T., Choudhary R., Kulkarni P. Isolation and Screening of Cellulase Producing Bacteria from Sugar Industry Waste //Research Journal of Agricultural Sciences (July). – 2024. – C. 918-921.

10. Abdusamatov, S., Jabborova, D., Azimova, N., Alimov, J. E., Djalolova, B., Alhewairini, S. S., ... & Davranov, K. Eco-Friendly Biodegradation of Plant Biomass Using Multienzyme-Producing *Trichoderma harzianum* for Sustainable Feed Improvement: S. Abdusamatov et al //Waste and Biomass Valorization. – 2026. – T. 17. – №. 2. – C. 931-942.
11. Kumar, A., Saharan, B.S., Parshad, J., Gera, R., Choudhary, J., Yadav, R.: Revolutionizing Indian agriculture: the imperative of advanced biofertilizer technologies for sustainability. *Dis Agri* 2(1), 24 (2024)
12. Abdusamatov, S. A., Jabborova, D., Azimova, N. S., Kuziev, S., Alimov, J. E., Jalolova, B. S., ... & Sheoran, A. R. Exploring the Potential of *Trichoderma harzianum* THNUU-1 for bio-Valorization of Agricultural Waste //Waste and Biomass Valorization. – 2025. – T. 16. – №. 9. – C. 4995-5006.
13. Green M. R., Sambrook J. Isolation of high-molecular-weight DNA using organic solvents //Cold Spring Harbor Protocols. – 2017. – T. 2017. – №. 4. – C. pdb. prot093450.
14. Schoch, C. L., Seifert, K. A., Huhndorf, S., Robert, V., Spouge, J. L., Levesque, C. A., ... & White, M. M Nuclear ribosomal internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region as a universal DNA barcode marker for Fungi //Proceedings of the national academy of Sciences. – 2012. – T. 109. – №. 16. – C. 6241-6246.